

PROMOTING CERVICAL CANCER SCREENING IN TRANSGENDER MALES: BARRIERS TO CARE

Maggie Weiss DNP RN WHCNP-BC; Chair Kathleen Hinoki PhD, RN; Committee Penny Weismuller DrPH, RN

Statement of Problem

- National Guidelines for cervical cancer (CC) screening have significantly decreased mortality rates in women
- Transgender Males (TM) often do not get screened, resulting in the potential for late diagnosis of GYN malignancies
- TMs do not feel comfortable disclosing sexual orientation (SO) and gender identity (GI); healthcare providers (HCP) fail to meet needs due to lack of knowledge and/or experience with TMs

Purpose

To assess whether the introduction of new gender neutral intake forms increased the offering and conduct of annual gynecologic screenings for the TM population

Framework

The Process of Cultural Competence in the Delivery of Healthcare Services (PCCDHS): A Model of Care by Josepha Campinha-Bacote (2002)

Examples of SOGI

Examples of Sexual Orientation Questions:

- Do you think of yourself as:*
- Straight or heterosexual
 - Lesbian, gay, or homosexual
 - Bisexual
 - Something else
 - Don't know or choose not to disclose

Examples of Gender Identity Questions:

- What is your current Gender Identity? (check one)*
- Male/Female
 - Transgender Male/Trans Man/Female-to-Male FTM
 - Transgender Female/Trans Woman/Male-to-Female (MTF)
 - Genderqueer, neither exclusively male nor female
 - Choose not to disclose

What sex were you assigned at birth on your original birth certificate? (check one)

- Male
- Female
- Choose not to disclose

Retrieved from <https://www.lgbthealtheducation.org/wp-content/uploads/Collecting-Sexual-Orientation-and-Gender-Identity-Data-in-EHRs-2016.pdf>

Methods/Abstraction Tool

- Evaluate pre-and post-implementation of SOGI sensitive intake forms from January 1 to December 31, 2013 and from January 1 to December 31, 2016
- Goal to identify whether TMs who self-identified were offered CC screening (pap smear), and if ordered, was screening performed by HCP within the primary care department

Findings

Despite implementation of SOGI forms, the number of GYN health screenings did not improve

Implications for Practice

- Have SOGI be part of the health history and incorporate SOGI forms into the electronic medical record
- Establish a transgender champion, liaison or resource person in the healthcare facility
- Provide education and resources to providers on transgender healthcare needs

Recommendations

- More studies needed on this topic:
 - using a larger sample size
 - using multiple sites
- Future studies should focus on:
 - factors that encourage TMs to disclose
 - factors that make HCPs more likely to offer GYN screenings

Results

- **2013**
 - Completed screenings: 62.5%
 - Did not receive counseling: 12.5%
 - Declined CC screening: 25%

- **2016**
 - Completed screenings: 52.6%
 - Did not receive counseling: 26.4%
 - Declined CC screening: 21%